

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Nduwimana**FIRST NAME:** Jean Marie Vianney**PROGRAM CODE:** PHGH**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord on Windows 7)

MASTERING ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

EUCLID University developed a coursepack on academic writing for its doctoral students. Worldwide, doctorate degree holders are usually involved in careers where they are expected to make regular scientific publications. A sound academic writing is of outstanding significance to produce an attractive paper for publication. However, it seems like many students come to university with a misunderstanding concerning the concept of academic writing as well as very bad habits from their previous studies and working experience. These bad habits coupled with misunderstanding regarding academic writing could lead to a significant negative impact on students' ability to write a sound scientific paper. Furthermore, some students have different writing styles acquired from their academic and professional background. In order to address such challenges, harmonize miscellaneous academic backgrounds and avail world class doctoral graduates, EUCLID University highly focuses on the skills required for an excellent academic writing. These skills comprise of blending the content of any academic paper in addition to a well-structured and highly organized work. To make this happen, EUCLID University committed to produce high quality doctoral graduates, hence it developed for them an academic writing coursepack. In this response paper, I will share the knowledge gained from the EUCLID academic writing coursepack as well as a brief critical personal evaluation of the content of this coursepack and its structure.

2) SHARED KNOWLEDGE AND SKILLS IN ACADEMIC WRITING

a) The Table of Contents Layout

The table of contents in this coursepack is widely detailed highlighting the topics to be covered by the student. A sixty-six pages document provides through its contents a broad range of points the learner is expected to cover in order to deepen the academic writing knowledge and skills.

b) Chapter One: Essay Writing

Regarding the chapter one on essay writing on this coursepack, it provides the aim of an academic essay as well as basic steps to follow in writing an essay. There is an important emphasis of taking note in addition to the source of information having in mind the question to answer. Apart from an important notion of organizing essay ideas into a sound plan, the document also highlights the clear aspect of creative thinking versus critical thinking during the essay writing. Furthermore, the coursepack calls attention to essay structure with a sound approach to construct essay paragraphs. To close the chapter on essay writing, the course focuses on three important aspects. The first one is to remind the use of an excellent academic habit of referencing the essay to stay away from plagiarism. The second well-developed and very important aspect is concerned with editing the essay by checking carefully its content as well as its structure. The third aspect deals with handing the essay in with a reminder that an assignment is completed when it is submitted where and to whom it must be. Finally, a list of references for essay writing in this coursepack is provided at the end of this chapter so that it could be used by the readers.

c) Chapter Two: Plagiarism

Concerning the chapter two of the coursepack, it deals with the concept of plagiarism in academic writing. Above all, the author defines the concept of plagiarism, gives specific examples of plagiarism as well as when and why to mention the source of information in writing. Second, the course highlights the way to use in text citation, short quotations in addition to long quotations with supporting examples. Third, the approach of paraphrasing with acceptable and unacceptable examples to illustrate it is also presented (EUCLID 2019a, 8). Note that there is also a focus regarding when to not cite in addition to signal phrases to introduce quotations or paraphrasing. Finally in this chapter, besides citations, this coursepack provides a way of dealing with a list of work cited and the format to follow (EUCLID 2019a, 10).

d) Chapter Three: Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers

With regard to chapter three, it addresses some rules of thumb for writing papers. At the beginning, the author suggests a clear statement of the main thesis as well as staying focused on some important aspect to assess. In the same way, the writer must neither lead with nor conclude or include sweeping generalities in an academic paper. Furthermore, it is of outstanding significance to write clearly and avoid esoteric words, neologisms, or polysyllabophilia in order to avoid hard to decipher writing style (EUCLID 2019a, 14). The rules of thumb for writing papers also include taking seriously the views of other writers without misinterpretations, the use of the first person singular whenever needed, in addition to supporting assertions to avoid plagiarism (EUCLID 2019a, 16).

e) Chapter Four: Literature Review

Under the chapter four in this coursepack, it talks about the aspect of literature review. First of all, the author highlights eleven important reminders concerning mainly the use of punctuation while writing. Secondly, the writer shows the way to use an apostrophe, the difference between “its” and “it’s”, as well as the difference between “your” and “you’re” in order to mark the possession (EUCLID 2019a, 19). Thirdly, the coursepack focuses attention on the use of “that” as per compared to “which” and the need of coma before a conjunction in a list of items. Likewise, there is a need to focus attention on when to write numbers out or to use numerals as well. Towards the end the chapter, the author compares and contrasts the use of “a” versus “an”, “good” versus “well”, “I” versus “me” along with the focus on the situation to use the conjunction “and” at the beginning of a sentence (EUCLID 2019a, 22).

f) Chapter Five: What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One?

With respect to chapter five, it talks about the style guide and the reason why the writer would need it. The chapter shows that the style guide should be an invaluable tool for any writer and it also provides some different aspects the style can encompass. Further, it highlights that EUCLID recommends the use of Chicago styles to its students. This section finally gives some free technical styles to check for a deep understanding of this topic (EUCLID 2019a, 25).

g) Chapter Six: American vs. British English Basic Differences and Influences of Change

The chapter six covers the American as compared to British English with basic differences and influences of change. The chapter starts by giving the main reasons the

American English is currently the dominant influence on its counterpart British English worldwide. Next, it gives clear examples illustrating different pronunciation despite similar spelling as well as different spelling though same pronunciation (EUCLID 2019a, 27). Thereafter, the author focuses on same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation in addition to same words, but different or additional meanings. Later, the chapter put emphasis on grammar, syntax, punctuation, general usage with also a focus on the situation of the same concept, different terms or expressions; or same words, differences in style, connotation and frequency. It presents some examples concerning euphemistic references, equality vocabulary and politically correct references. This chapter also presented the aspects of ethnolects, Yiddish and ethnic Jewish influence, together with various jargons and changing cultural references. Finally, the author talks a little bit about regional variation, identity, stereotyping; four-letter words, obscenities along with specific examples of differences with punctuation and dates (EUCLID 2019a, 34).

h) Chapter Seven: Sample Corrections to Papers

Concerning the chapter seven in this coursepack, it considers the topic of sample corrections to papers. At the beginning, it presents an introduction showing the intent of a paper consisting of an outlook for Eritrean economy during the challenge of global economy. Later, the chapter describes the way the US recession will make an impact on other countries' economy by mainly affecting emerging markets as well as commodity exporters (EUCLID 2019a, 40). Further, the writer put emphasis on important features of a sound curriculum vitae in addition to the way to write it in order to attract the employer's attention on the quality of a job seeker (EUCLID 2019a, 42).

i) Chapter Eight: CMS Crib Sheet

As regards the chapter eight, it covers the CMS crib sheet with explanation concerning the use of Chicago Manual of Style. The writer highlights the Chicago style and usage, Chicago page formatting as well as Chicago Endnotes and Footnotes. Regarding the Chicago style and usage, it addresses the use of abbreviations, capitalization, compound words, emphasis using italics or quotes, numbers and dates, as well as quotations (EUCLID 2019a, 46). In respect to Chicago page format, the author explains the way to make footnotes, the features of quality tables as well as headings and lists (EUCLID 2019a, 49). Lastly, the chapter points on Chicago Endnotes, footnotes together with bibliographies with respect to a variety of sources such as books, journals, reports, newspapers, and so forth.

j) Chapter Nine: Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

Finally, the last section of this coursepack consists of chapter nine talking about Latin abbreviations and expressions. It is a short chapter depicting tables of Latin usage

with the equivalent English for the common Latin abbreviations used in writing together with commonly used Latin expressions (EUCLID 2019a, 56).

3) MY REACTION ON THE EUCLID'S ACADEMIC WRITING COURSEPACK

a) Preliminary Pages

In scholarly writing and mainly at EUCLID, the form of a paper is extremely important with a set of standardized features (EUCLID 2019b, 4). At the outset, page numbering is one of the aspects to consider while dealing with the structure of an academic writing. In this coursepack, the cover page is numbered using uppercase Roman numeral namely Page | I. In my opinion, page numbering should be omitted on this cover page like. In addition, front matter pages between the cover page and the chapter 1 in this document are also numbered using uppercase Roman numerals from Page | II to Page | V. From my academic writing background, I should number these pages with lowercase Roman numerals i, ii, iii, and iv respectively. As far as front matter pages are concerned, the table of contents seems to be poorly structured. In this regard, I really appreciate the way the chapter one on essay writing is presented with its six headings. However, the remaining chapters are not presenting headings and subheadings in a proper format. As clear and non exhaustive examples, the chapter dealing with plagiarism comprises of unnumbered twenty six heading over only four pages. I prefer reducing these headings to a half and numbering them using the Arabic numbers in the format 2.1., 2.2., and so forth with subheadings such as 2.1.1., 2.1.2., and so on wherever needed. I find the opposite example under chapter seven where running text extends from page 36 to page 44 with only one heading. In my opinion, I should organize the paragraphs into headings and subheadings to attract my readers. In summary, the table of contents for this coursepack seems to be really cumbersome and poorly organized and could be referred to as a messy table of contents.

b) Chapter One: Essay Writing

Regarding the chapter one on essay writing, its content provides a good guide to write an essay. I appreciated the way the coursepack provided a clear essay structure, approach to write sound paragraphs as well as tips for effective writing. I am especially moved by the approach suggested for editing the essay to make it as improved as possible before its completion. I am also impressed by the emphasis to hand in the essay since the assignment is not completed until is submitted (EUCLID 2019a, 4).

However, I did not like some aspects regarding mainly the form on this document. In my opinion, I should use on page one the heading "Introduction" instead of "What does a good essay need?" On the same page, I prefer to remove the framed text on the basic steps in writing an essay and present it as a separate paragraph under the heading of

introduction. I should also proceed in the same way wherever such framed texts are presented all over this chapter.

As a noticeable general remark in this document, there is a need to use a proper punctuation, to harmonize the font size, and to avoid the use of contracted forms (Barker 2013, 120). Another apparent remark on the page one and on subsequent pages is the way the coursepack is providing some references to consider. As an example, the reference provided as “see The Learning Centre guide ‘Answering Assignment Questions’” should be presented in any other academic reference style such as Turabian, Harvard, APA, and so forth. Remember that not only the content of an academic document is important but also its form is of outstanding significance (EUCLID 2019b, 4).

Regarding the heading dealing with handing in the essay, the author seems to give a reach content but in a poor writing structure. In my opinion, not only the heading should not be presented as a framed text but also there is poor punctuation in its first paragraph. This heading should be placed at the same level as the preceding heading concerning editing the essay. Finally, the fact of giving a list of references at the end of this chapter does not work for me because there is neither in text referencing nor footnote in all text (EUCLID 2019a, 4). In this case, I should manage to progressively insert references in the running text in order to feel comfortable to provide a bibliography that does not happen in a vacuum at the end.

c) Chapter Two: Plagiarism

Concerning the chapter two dealing with plagiarism, the author is successful to make me feel comfortable with the concept of this topic of interest. First of all, I appreciate the way the author defines the concept of plagiarism with clear examples as well as providing explanation regarding when, why, and how to give the source of information to avoid plagiarism. Second, I enjoy the focus on quotations since it is my first time to learn that long quotations more than four lines are cited in a separate and indented paragraph. Third, I equally value the way unacceptable as well as acceptable paraphrasing are presented. Lastly, I acknowledge the fact highlighting the list of work cited and particularly the way to follow to achieve a logical flow (EUCLID 2019a, 13).

On the contrary, as I initially mentioned in the opening paragraph about my reaction to this coursepack, I do not like the writing structure of this chapter with cumbersome and poorly organized headings. With respect to the content, the author failed to convince me about the in-text citing style. In fact, the author of this chapter highlights that to cite something in text, the writer only needs to put in parenthesis the author’s name along with the page number of the source of information (EUCLID 2019a, 6). In my opinion and as per EUCLID guidelines, there is a need to put in parenthesis not only the author’s name, but also the year of publication as well as the page number of the source of information (EUCLID 2019b, 8). Further, the example supporting the citation of the long quotation is not following the rules in accordance with the author of this chapter. In this case, the illustration of a long quotation provided is a non indented paragraph comprising of six lines while it must be indented (EUCLID 2019a, 7).

Despite a clear emphasis regarding paraphrases as well as when to cite, I do not like the way the author presents it mainly the writing style, bullets, and punctuations. Similarly, the author provides the format to follow for works cited, but I was not successfully convinced. As an example, the author presents the format to follow without giving details on the referencing style being used. On this occasion, the document also provides an example of the method exempting the writer from the need to show the works cited or references at the end of the paper. In my opinion, works cited or references must always be provided to the readers.

d) Chapter Three: Some Rules of Thumb for Writing Papers

With regard to chapter three on some rules of thumb for writing papers, I generally appreciate the content of this chapter. The author makes me understand the basic points to remember while writing papers. I especially support the crucial emphasis on writing clearly by avoiding esoteric words, neologisms, or polysyllabophilia in order to convey comprehensible ideas to readers (EUCLID 2019a, 14).

In contrast, I am not convinced with the writing style of some paragraphs. For instance, the author iteratively used punctuation that seems to be inappropriate. Similarly, it seems to be too much paragraphs while there should be an integration of some of them. With reference to paragraphs, I think I should merge the last three paragraphs into one paragraph under this chapter (EUCLID 2019a, 16). Moreover, based on what I know, a long sentence is not the one comprising of more than five lines as the author mentioned in this chapter (EUCLID 2019a, 15). In general, the writer must avoid the use of long sentences exceeding three lines (EUCLID 2019b, 8).

e) Chapter Four: Literature Review

Under the chapter four of this coursepack, the focus is on the literature review in academic writing. To begin with this chapter, the author convinced me concerning the eleven important reminders mainly pointing on punctuation while writing. Thereafter, the writer was successful to make me understand the grammar rules of possession, the use of relative pronouns “that” and “which”, as well as the need of a comma before a conjunction. Specifically, I am impressed by the way the author compares and contrasts the use of “I” versus “me” and the situation where to write out numbers or to use numerals (EUCLID 2019a, 22). Personally, I have been committing mistakes and wrongly using “I” or “me” in my daily English grammar.

However, the author does not satisfy me regarding a number of points in this chapter. First and foremost, I did not like the writing style mainly some inappropriate headings in addition to inadequate paragraphs comprising of some one or two lines only. Secondly, regarding the content, the author seems to provide some non convincing illustrations. As a typical case, the writer gives two similar examples a hundred per cent to compare and contrast formal way and modern way of using a comma before a

conjunction (EUCLID 2019a, 20). In the same way, I do not understand the connection between the heading discussing numbers or numerals and its paragraphs talking about the use of “a” versus “an”, “well” versus “good” under this heading (EUCLID 2019a, 21). Finally, on my opinion, the content discussed under the chapter four does nothing to do with the so called literature review. In fact, literature review consists of a critical search and review of a variety of relevant sources in order to make clear the current situation on a particular research topic of interest (Greener and Martelli 2015, 25). Thus, the content of this chapter seems to be off topic compared with its title and is instead dealing with English grammar.

f) Chapter Five: What is a Style Guide, and Why Would I Need One?

In respect with the chapter five, it talks about the style guide and the reasons why the writer needs it. On the one hand, I am mainly impressed with the different aspects a style guide can encompass. On the other hand, I do not appreciate some other aspects as per presented in this chapter. Specifically, it is a chapter comprising of two pages with a running text lacking any single heading while it is unacceptable to write a long running text without headings (EUCLID 2019b, 6). Additionally, the author came up with free downloadable economist as well as BBC News styles guides (EUCLID 2019a, 25). As far as these free downloadable style guides are concerned, my point of view is that it should be better to issue public health related style guides since other styles seem to be irrelevant and add nothing special other than inundate the learner.

g) Chapter Six: American vs. British English Basic Differences and Influences of Change

The chapter six covers the American as compared to its counterpart British English with basic differences and influences of change. Overall, the explanations provided in the introduction convinced me regarding the reasons why the American English is now dominant over the British English (EUCLID 2019a, 27).

In contrast, there is at many levels the poor writing structure such as one line paragraph, irrelevant punctuation, non international abbreviations without their meanings, and so on. Apart from poor writing structure, some other aspects that the author used did not work for me because there are many examples under different headings without clarifying whether it is American or British English. In this case, examples for euphemistic references, equality vocabulary, politically correct references and so forth are not clear to me whether they are American or British English (EUCLID 2019a, 32). In addition, the author was not successful in making me feel that some of his illustrations are really politically correct references. For instance, the writer used the word “seniors” to mean “older” or the expression “animal companion” to mean “pet” (EUCLID 2019a, 32). In my opinion, I should consider these examples as euphemistic references since they are polite forms and have nothing to do with politics. I also noticed that the heading

“same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation” is a little bit confusing since I cannot understand what it intends to refer to up to now.

On the thirtieth page number, as the author continues to compare and contrast American and British English, he issued a sentence stating that “He’s in the hospital with a broken leg.” and he labeled it as being a British English style. In front of this sentence, the writer exactly repeated the same phrase from A to Z while labeling it as being American English style. My point of view is that all these sentences are completely similar. Finally, at the end of this chapter on page number 35, the author seems to develop a point on the punctuation with business (formal) versus social (informal) letters. But, I am disappointed by this point because neither the business style nor the social one was shown.

h) Chapter Seven: Sample Corrections to Papers

The chapter seven in this coursepack developed the topic of sample corrections to papers. I appreciated the introduction paragraphs showing the intent of the first paper consisting of the Eritrea economy amidst the challenge of global economy. The writer was successful to make me understand the way the US recession will ultimately affect the economy of other countries on all continents (EUCLID 2019a, 40). Regarding the second paper talking about the quality of a sound curriculum vitae, my favorite part was the focus to design it without exceeding two pages because I usually used to make it too long to reach even five pages (EUCLID 2019a, 42).

Nevertheless, I think that some aspects of this chapter are not developed as smart as possible. Overall, it seems not presentable to use only and only one heading to cover a running text consisting of seven pages (EUCLID 2019b, 6). Also note that this only heading, namely “introduction and summary”, is somehow strange since, based on what I know, the word summary should usually come at the end of a given discussion and not in introduction. Furthermore, I did not understand the connection between the closing paragraph between the paper on US recession and the opening paragraph on the curriculum vitae (EUCLID 2019a, 40). It is clear that the writer was trying to start a new paper discussion, but the lack of transition word made the document a little bit confusing. Bear in mind that the reader cannot guess the introduction of a new paper, since a fortiori there is no closing clause regarding Eritrea economy as it was the main purpose of the first paper. Consequently, at this level, I strongly believe that there is a need to add a subheading to benchmark the separation between both sample papers. In summary, this chapter has an average good content but its writing structure makes it look like a little bit confusing.

i) Chapter Eight: CMS Crib Sheet

In respect to chapter eight addressing the Chicago Manual of Style, it is really a topic of outstanding significance as the academic writing is concerned. Firstly, under Chicago usage style, I am impressed by the way the chapter explained the capitalization

mainly the use of full caps as well as heading caps because I have been only using so far the sentence caps throughout the writing of my papers. In the same way, I acquired new knowledge with reference to the proper utilization of a hyphen in compound words particularly with the prefixes (EUCLID 2019a, 46). I similarly become acquainted with the proper use of italics, quotations marks, spelling out numbers versus using numerals, as well as quotations (EUCLID 2019a, 46). I appreciated the way to highlight the emphasis in quotations by adding notes such as [emphasis was added] or [emphasis in the original] as it was my first time to learn this remark. Secondly, regarding Chicago page formats, the author was successful in making me master the way to design a smart final manuscript, the aspects of footnotes, the features of quality tables, the headings and lists as well (EUCLID 2019a, 49). Thirdly, this section of the coursepack makes me understand the Chicago Endnotes, Footnotes along with bibliographies for different types of sources and I feel comfortable to get very soon familiar with the style as I will keep using it.

However, I feel I should address some elements provided in this coursepack. Initially, the chapter title namely “CMS Crib Sheet” contains the acronym that could confuse readers. Based on my knowledge, the writer must spell out the full term in text during its first use with its acronym in parenthesis, and thereafter use the same acronym in subsequent phrases to represent the full term (EUCLID 2019a, 44). Next, at the end of this chapter, there is a sentence stating that “all health and success does me good, however far off and withdrawn it may appear; all disease and failure helps to make me sad and does me evil, however much sympathy it may have with me or I with it.-- Thoreau [*sic*]”. In fact, not only I do not understand the connection between this sentence and the chapter of interest, but also the phrase seems syntactically incorrect in my opinion. Apart from these remarks I suggest to address in this chapter, I acknowledge that it is well designed and it adds to my existing knowledge with regard to referencing styles since I have only been using Harvard as well as Vancouver referencing during my previous studies.

j) Chapter Nine: Latin Abbreviations and Expressions

Lastly, the chapter nine of this coursepack describes the Latin abbreviations and expressions. At the beginning, I appreciate the remark putting emphasis on the use of plain English in order to avoid misinterpretation of the readers. Further, the tables depicting English equivalent of common Latin abbreviations as well as commonly used Latin expressions are well designed and clear to readers. In my opinion, the author was successful in making me feel comfortable with the content of this chapter.

4) CONCLUSION

I acknowledge that scholarly writing is far and foremost an invaluable skill for doctoral students to help them develop their self-confidence as future potential writers. Despite an ever increasing change in technology regarding the way researchers are engaged in scientific investigations, the writing styles as well as the words they use to

communicate their information are of outstanding significance. In line with these knowledge and skills development, the academic writing coursepack as per prepared by EUCLID for doctoral students is an important source to strengthen scholarly writing abilities. I find that its scientific content coupled with miscellaneous papers from different sources raise the reader's awareness to make a critical thinking as well as getting acquainted with the topic. I would recommend the coursepack to everyone aspiring to master the writing style for paper publication. As practice makes perfect, the use of this course material together with other related documents will equip the learners with required knowledge and skills to overcome challenging experiences in academic writing.

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